

AN EVALUATION OF ENGLISH TEXTBOOK AT MATRICULATION LEVEL IN MULTAN DIVISION, PAKISTAN

Sadia Gulzarⁱ

NCBA&E Multan, Pakistan

Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the English textbook at matriculation level in Multan Division in terms of content, vocabulary, grammar, exercises, activities and physical makeup of the textbook as well as context and information for teachers to guide the teachers. For this purpose, close ended questionnaire was used to collect data from one hundred and eight teachers. Data was analyzed to find out percentages of each items and graphs and it was found that overall quality of textbook is good. Content, vocabulary, exercises and grammar rules are organized logically. To guide the teachers, sufficient information is provided in the textbook. The textbook is per course goals and needs of the students. Textbook is good enough to promote critical thinking of the students and in the textbook images is not so high aesthetic quality. Though majority of teachers are satisfied with this textbook but minority of teachers who do not agree with this, cannot be neglected. There is still need to improve textbook. Finally, it can be said that the overall quality of textbook is good.

Keywords: grade-X English, ESL, criteria for ESL textbook evaluation, Punjab

1. Introduction

English is taught in the public and private schools of Punjab at matriculation level as a compulsory subject like other school level classes. In Board exams, the success rate in English subject is low as compared to other subjects. There is need to evaluate present course books of English of Grade-X for overall improvement and make it interesting for the students. Grade X English textbook is taught in public and private schools in Punjab and this English book is published by the Punjab Textbook Board Lahore. This book

ⁱ Correspondence: email sadinain@gmail.com

consists of total thirteen units in which three lessons contain poems and remaining are prose. In this English book, the guidelines of National Curriculum 2006 are followed. An effort has been made to include to competencies, standards, and benchmarks mentioned in the curriculum document. The basic requirements of reading and thinking skills, writing skills, oral communication and formal and lexical aspects of language have been incorporated in all units.

Textbook is frequently used as the most important teaching tool because it can determine not only what will be taught but also how it will be taught. Although television, computer, internet and other new media are rivaling printed materials of communication yet textbooks remains major source of information in schools and colleges. Among various instructional aids, supplementary book is presumably the most important because it is used in formal as well as informal situations of instruction and also in the situation of self-study. This is the cheapest of all the above mentioned aids for the students and also for the teachers.

It is hard to define the role of textbook in language classroom accurately. For meeting students' needs, it is not satisfactory way to use only textbook without any supplementary material. But it is very clear that students and teachers need a framework. It is important that textbook provides organized objective base instructions but it does not mean that teachers should be slaves to their text. It is fact that language classrooms use the textbook in order to meet the goals of the program. Textbook are used to develop the communicative competence by providing the authentic and effective language tasks. Textbook can be understood as a window through which students can develop the communicative competence from a little classroom to a broad social context. Textbook is a major tool to enable the learners to progress but it is not true that only textbook is sufficient enough for the learner's needs.

Teachers who teach the same course can provide good ideas and information to each other. Authors try to meet the objectives but their choices may differ in terms of skimming and approaches to the text, therefore it is important to know what books are available in the market before selecting a text of private publisher. First important thing is to consider the table of contents in order to know the teaching philosophy and course curriculum. For this purpose, consider the following questions:

1. Is the content of topics broad or specific?
2. Are key principles listed clearly and precisely?
3. Do the interpretations and explanations meet with the teaching style?

Textbooks differ from the level of difficulty in terms of readability, depth of theoretical information and the problems of chapter-ending complexity. Textbooks are helpful to provide the insight to deal with these issues whether there are errors and negative effects on students' learning or textbooks are helpful to determine such effects.

It is true that the only available resource to the students and teachers is the textbook. Chapter summaries and solution to textbook problems should be in separate study guide. Soft-wares accompanied with textbook are becoming popular. Such soft-wares differ from each other in terms of usefulness and quality but it is important to ask for demonstration before purchasing these soft-wares. In Pakistan these software are not available and far away.

Apache speaking scholars developed two experimental language learning textbooks collaborative from San Carlos and White Mountain reservations. Grammar – Translation tradition was used in writing as one type of text and was modeled after Zepeda’s Papago Grammar and Wilson’s Conversational Navajo workbook. The other type of text was based on Asher’s (1982) teachers’ guide book in which total physical response method was used to teach Apache. A variety of problems was raise by both approaches which were solved by a judicious combination of the both approaches. For example, grammar translation method is the best to teach verbs supplemented by exercise of total physical response style whereas total physical response exercises are used to teach syntactic structure and yes-no questions supplemented by grammatical explanations. Along with these methods, native experts should monitor the text to avoid politically or culturally inappropriate and sensitive material. At final stage, there is a need to establish a dialogue between native experts and linguists in terms of making decision about the degree to which linguistic terminology is best handled in each curriculum.

It is understood that language renewal is not possible through the aids of efficient and sufficient books. The tool of Western Imperialism is justified in terms of books whereas Native American cultures are not book cultures. But these Native American cultures have always adopted foreign cultural elements for their own advantages. For example in recent decades, the computer is the more efficient source of transportation is an educational tool. Would it be wise decision to depend on computer technology to preserve the languages? This point illustrates that we can go back and search for whether language renewal is possible through a good tool as text books but it may possible that some people will never ready to admit that books are useful. It is known that textbooks will be useful to some learners as only part of the time.

No doubt, it has been said that successful language renewal can be the best achieved if parents convince to just speak the language to their children and nothing. No school curriculum programme can remove this. We should make second language textbooks and second language curriculum as attractive and efficient as we can. This is the issue of English language in the most of Pakistan. Seldom addressed skills in the textbooks are listening and speaking skills and even these are missed. On the basis of two Apache text problems it was recommended and solved by judicious combination of

two approaches that grammar translation method is the best to teach verbs, supplemented by exercises of total physical response style and total physical response exercises are used to teach syntactic structure and yes-no questions, supplemented by grammatical explanations.

It was also suggested that native experts should monitor the text to avoid culturally inappropriate material and finally there should be a dialogue between native experts and linguists to determine the degree to which linguistic terminology is best handled in each curriculum. From this experience, we can learn a lot of our languages; such experiences must be reflected in our language textbooks by using the conversational method and grammar translation method even in Urdu or Punjabi / Sindhi textbooks.

2. Research Questions

The following are research questions;

1. Is the textbook appropriate for the curriculum and does it meet with the course goals?
2. Is the cover of the textbook appealing and images are attractive?
3. Are the information for the teachers provided in the textbook sufficient to guide?
4. Is the subject matter presented in logical and organized manner and does the content serves as the window to the target language culture?
5. Do the grammar rules and vocabulary words present in the increasing order of difficulty and in variety of ways?
6. Do the exercises promote critical thinking of the students and activities facilitate students' use of grammar rules by creating situations?

This study aims:

- 1- To check appropriateness of grade-X English textbook for the curriculum.
- 2- To check the layout of the textbook and quality of images.
- 3- To check whether sufficient guidance is provided to teachers in the textbook or not.
- 4- To check logical organization of subject matter.
- 5- To check whether grammar rules and vocabulary in the textbook are presented in increasing order of difficulty or not.
- 6- To know whether exercises of book promote critical thinking and students use grammar rules by creating situation or not.

3. Significance of the Study

This study would be useful for teachers, students, textbook designers and educational experts. They may review the content of teaching according to student's needs. Teachers may also improve the teaching methodologies as well as assessment methods in English language teaching classrooms. Teachers may adopt appropriate methods according to level of students.

4. Literature Review

It is a debatable point among professionals whether and how to use textbooks in teaching English as a Second Language. The significance of textbook still stands through quality generated material developed by new technologies and each year a series of new text books are published by the industry. A textbook is very important for the teacher due to different purposes such as a source of reading material and attractive activities as proposed by curriculum itself Allwright, R. (1990).

a) Criteria for ESL Textbook Evaluation

Williams D. (1983) in Bello University, Nigeria in his article proposed criteria to evaluate ESL textbook. A framework was advocated for evaluation to take considerable points, first assumptions about second language teaching and second linguistic, technical and pedagogical criteria relevant to assumptions.

b) Scheme for Evaluation

Scheme is based on four assumptions. The scheme for evaluation links a set of general, technical, pedagogical and linguistic criteria to second language teaching assumptions.

c) Up-to-date Methodology

The ESL textbook should be correlated with linguistics and psychological principles beneath accepted and current methods of second language teaching.

d) Guidelines for Non-native Teachers

For non-native English teachers, the textbook should serve proper guidance. Procedures concerned as doubtful proposed by textbook could not be left over the untrained or partially trained teachers who have not controlled over all aspects of English language like natives. On the other hand, the teacher may ignore the writer's intention for pronunciation practice for such items as 'live/leave'; but the teacher may teach such items as the meanings of the minimal pair.

e) Needs of Second Language Learners

In multilingual setting, it can be a complex task to cater the needs of second language learner when English is the second or third or fourth language and pupils have

different mother tongues in the same class. ESL textbook writers have cut out their work. In some cases, there is a need of distinction between English as a medium of instruction or English as a subject.

f) Relevance to the Socio-Cultural Environment

In learning vocabulary and syntax there are second language learning problems that arise due to difference between culture association with mother tongue and the target language. Usage and acceptability in some areas can be determined by socio-cultural norms. Because of world wide spread of English ESL textbook writers should be sensitive in the usage.

g) Checklist of Items

The evaluation scheme is used to form a checklist of items. For guiding non-native teachers, there are seven principles with linguistic, general and technical criteria. The textbook should give guidance for presenting items and skills of a language. For the teaching of pronunciations, the textbook should provide aids. For teaching grammar structure, the textbook should provide a variety of techniques and meaningful situations.

The textbook should differentiate the different skills which are involved in vocabulary teaching. The textbook should guide for presenting the reading comprehension passages.

The textbook should present the different techniques to guide the content in writing exercises. The textbook should include diagrams, pictures and tables.

h) Review the Skills Presented in the Textbook

The main purpose of ESL program is to enhance the language skills of a learner. But it is more important to seek the answers of the questions, which skills are taught and how they are taught. For this reason, review of the textbook is considered as necessary to evaluate the skills acquired by the learners. So the effectiveness of textbook is concerned with the questions as;

1. Does the text is consistent with the skills, it claims to focus on?
2. Does it teach the skills or students already have?

i) Evaluate the Exercises and Activities in the Textbook

To review the effectiveness of textbook exercises and activities from questions should be answered. Do the activities and exercises play a major role to learner's language acquisition? It may be possible that exercises and activities are helpful for the teachers but cannot get benefit from them. The exercises and activities in the textbook should provide the opportunities for the students to practice the language skills for example to negotiate for meaning in English as information gap or role plays. Such activities may be helpful for the development of speaking skills in the students. Through such activities the students would be able to negotiate in real life context.

Does the format of exercise contain both free and controlled practice? Free practice refers to those activities in which a chance is given to the students to extend their experiences with language but in controlled practice answers are involved in fill in the blanks grammar activity, answers are limited to students' knowledge. It may also include open-ended discussion questions but in more structured and guided way.

Are the exercises progressive as the students go through the textbook? Exercises should be formed on the psychological principle of learning from more simple to more difficult and complex in order to develop the skill continually stimulated and challenged. Are the exercises challenging? If the textbook is easier and more interested, the students would be motivated if there is something new in each chapter. Routine leads to boredom. The role of a textbook is a stimulus for communication.

j) Teacher's Guide

Teacher's guide is used to serve the teachers and to educate them. It is the basic source of development of teachers professionally. So, all textbooks should be in need of teacher's guide to facilitate the learning of students. For instance, teacher's guide provides the detailed explanation of concepts, teaching method and examples that facilitate learning.

k) Review of the Related Literature

Aftab, A. (2012) conducted a study on "*English Language Textbook Evaluation in Pakistan,*" to explore the situation of English language textbook in Pakistan at grade five by using mixed method approach. Two stages were preliminary staged on a small scale, including English language requirement survey and officials' interviews which were involved in publishing textbook. The evaluation of English syllables and curriculum, the detailed course book evaluation and the survey of the point of views of the users of the textbook were the main stages of the study.

During these stages, the criteria of evaluation questionnaires and checklists were derived from need analysis, materials development and curriculum design literature. This study put the light to the flams of educational area overall and these shortcomings were due to the poor standard of English which were actually prevailed in the country. The policies of the textbooks and curriculum were inappropriate. In general, the administrators and teachers lacked comprehension of teaching techniques, language learning objectives, syllabus design and materials. It was found that the textbook was depend on artificial and controlled activities for English language teaching. To conclude this study improvements were suggested in the developmental process of curriculum, textbook writers and teacher training programs and the textbook which can facilitate the acquisition of English language to the Pakistani learners

Kazim, S.S; Naseem, S. and Tabasum, S. (2015) conducted a study on "*Evaluation of English Textbook in Pakistan: A case study of Punjab Textbook for 9th Class*" in order to

evaluate English textbook for 9th class with the purpose to enquire the suitability of the textbook to provide the improvement of the English language programmers in the schools of Pakistan. Checklists would be used and it was found that the textbook did not fulfill the objectives of target language in general. It was argued that the textbook was definitely not meeting with the learners' needs. The textbook did not make any balance between four basic skills of language and the objectives. It lacked work book. In the textbook, least attention was given to pronunciation; activities regarding listening skills were not included. The textbook is not compatible with the requirements of improving fluency and promoting language skills. It was recommended that more attention was needed to be given to the textbooks of English language which are being utilized in language programs.

But this study focuses to evaluate English textbook at matriculation level in terms of the content, vocabulary, grammar, exercises, activities as well as the provided information for the teacher in order to examine the strong and weak points of textbook. Whether the textbook is per students' level and interest and the textbook content is effective enough for the learners or not.

5. Research Methodology

It was important to use a qualitative research approach for this study because of the reliance on individual perceptions of a particular language teaching. For this purpose, survey research design was selected to conduct this study to know the current opinion of teachers about Grade-X English Textbook.

a) Population of the Study

All teachers of English subject teaching at matriculation level in six thousand nine hundred and fifty-one (6951) male and female high and higher secondary schools of Punjab are population of this study. Punjab is divided into nine (9) divisions and thirty six (36) districts on administrative grounds. There are total six thousand nine hundred and fifty one (6951) high and higher secondary schools of male and female in Punjab. To collect data from all teachers of English subject in Punjab was very time, money consuming and difficult to approach. Out of nine divisions, only Multan division was selected to collect data. Multan division is further divided into four districts on administrative level. I collected data from those schools of Vehari, Multan and Khanewal who were easy to approach and accessible.

b) Selection of Sample

Since this study aims to evaluate the English textbook at matriculation level in Punjab therefore one hundred and eight (108) English subject teachers of matriculation level of public and private schools in Multan Division belonging to its three districts are

selected as research participants to obtain the required information. These teachers were selected because they were easy to contact and willingly available.

c) Description of Sample Population

In Punjab, English is taught at all levels in public and private schools. The present sample includes the teachers of matriculation level of both public and private schools of Multan division. In this sample, both male and female teachers are taken to provide the detailed information about the textbook.

d) Selection of Research Sites

The selection of participants was based on the following reasons in order to collect data for research;

1. To enhance the quality of education in Punjab, Pakistan, public and private schools are playing a vital role. For representation, both private and public schools in Punjab are selected.
2. The representation of public and private schools are taken at different districts of Punjab.
3. To represent both public and private schools they are selected as well as the male and female teachers are selected.
4. Feasibility is put forth to collect data, for this reason nearby district and tehsils are selected.

Due to the above reasons, the following public and private schools of different districts are selected as research sites.

Sr.No	Name of School	District	Public/Private
1	Govt. Islamia High School Vehari	Vehari	Public
2	Govt. Islamia Higher Secondary School Graha More	Vehari	Public
3	Hawks Girls Elementary School Mailsi	Vehari	Private
4	Govt. High School Colony Road Mailsi	Vehari	Public
5	Govt. Higher Secondary School Jalla Jeem	Vehari	Public
6	Govt. Girls High School Jalla Jeem	Vehari	Public
6	Govt. Girls High School Mailsi	Vehari	Public
7	Govt. Girls High School Chitani	Vehari	Public
8	Govt. Higher Secondary School Tibba	Vehari	Public
9	Govt. High School Chak 122/WB	Vehari	Public
10	Garrisons Grammar Higher Secondary School Multan	Multan	Private
11	Govt. Bukhari Public High School Multan	Multan	Public
12	Govt. Muslim High School Multan	Multan	Public
13	Govt. Comprehensive Higher Secondary School Multan	Multan	Public
14	Govt. Girls High School Haram Gate Multan	Multan	Public
15	Millennium School System Multan	Multan	Private
16	Garrisons Grammar Girls High School Multan	Multan	Private

17	Govt. Nusratul Islam Boys Higher Secondary School MTN	Multan	Public
18	Govt. High School Dolat Gate Multan	Multan	Public
19	Govt. Girls Higher Secondary Moonlight School Multan	Multan	Public
20	Govt. Atta Faiz-e –Aam High School Multan	Multan	Public
21	Model High School Jahanin	Khanewal	Private
22	Govt. Islamia High School Jahanin	Khanewal	Public
23	Govt. High School Jahania	Khanewal	Public
24	Govt. Girls High School Jahania	Khanewal	Public
25	Shaheen Public School Jahania	Khanewal	Private

e) Types of Questionnaire

There are close-ended questions in this questionnaire in order to get quantitative data. In each question, there are five options to choose from and the middle one is the midpoint between the two extremes.

f) Contents of Questionnaire

The contents were determined and selected by Prof. Ozcan Demiral in English Language Teaching department in Cyprus International University. The contents of this questionnaire are discussed with my supervisor Prof. dr. Naveed Ahmed and it was suggested to seek permission from the original author of this questionnaire. It was also directed to me by the supervisor to modify the questions regarding teacher's manual into the information provided for the teachers because at this level manuals are not provided but information is provided for the teachers to use the textbook appropriately.

g) Process of Data Collection

Questionnaires were distributed in the cities like Multan, Vehari, Mailsi and Jahania by hand and collected back by the same way. Total one hundred and twenty six questionnaires were sent out of which one hundred and eight received back. Return ratio of these questionnaires are nearly 88 percent.

6. Data Analysis

The first part of the questionnaire is divided into four portions and in these portions, there are close ended items about textbook's content, vocabulary and grammar, exercises, activities, attractiveness of the textbook and physical make up. The results show that the content of the textbook is arranged in a logical way, it helps to learn the culture of the target language, the content is selected through authentic pieces of literature as well as the real life issues are included in order to make the students be able to think critically so text is selected from a variety of literary genres consists of multiple structure of the sentence. Hence, it is fair to say that content selection is good.

Table and Figure 1: Teachers’ Opinion about Content

Excellent	Good	Adequate	Poor	Totally Lacking
42.35%	44.82%	23.62%	7.56%	0.76%

Second portion of part first was about vocabulary and grammar of the textbook. In this portion, there were total five questions. As for as vocabulary is concerned, vocabulary word are found in a logical manner more especially they are arranged easy to difficult in different varieties. In the textbook, text is organized in such a way that students are able to understand new words through the sequence of lessons. Hence, from figures it can be concluded that vocabulary and grammar of textbook is overall good.

Table and Figure 2: Teachers' Opinion about Vocabulary and Grammar

Excellent	Good	Adequate	Poor	Totally Lacking
19.65%	44.25%	24.58%	9.42%	2.05%

Third portion of part first is about the exercises and activities of the textbook. This portion consists of seven items. Mostly teachers convey the idea that through the exercises and activities are used during teaching. Exercises and activities facilitate the students to use grammar rules and also promote critical thinking of the students. So from results it is clear that quality of exercises and activities is good.

Table and Figure 3: Teachers' Opinion about Exercises and Activities

Excellent	Good	Adequate	Poor	Totally Lacking
20.06%	42.82%	26.46%	8.89%	1.73%

Fourth portion of part first was about attractiveness and physical make up of text book. There were four items in this portion. Lay out of the textbook is measured by its cover and visual imagery is good. Simple illustrations are used in the textbook are enough to understand the meaning and text is so attractive that students enjoy it while reading. Hence, attractiveness of the textbook and physical make up is “adequate”.

Table and Figure 4: Teachers' Opinion about Textbook and Physical Make-up

Excellent	Good	Adequate	Poor	Totally Lacking
16.07%	41.7%	32.76%	7.73%	1.65%

This section of the questionnaire was about “information for the teachers” provided in the textbook to help the teachers. This section was consisted four portions. The results show that information for the teachers are “good” to understand objective, methodology of the text and correct answer of the exercises are also provided in the textbook. It can also described that in “information for the teachers” teachers are guided how to use cues from morphology and context to help them in lexical inference in an “adequate” way.

This portion of part second of the questionnaire was about methodological guidance. This portion consists of three items. From results it is visible methodological guidance can be regard as “good” because in portion “information for the teachers” in the textbook teachers’ are given techniques to activate students background knowledge before reading the text and there are also sufficient examples in the textbook for preview, skimming, scanning, summarize and to find out main idea of the text.

Fourth portion of second part of questionnaire was about supplementary exercises and materials. This portion consists of three items. Guidance is provided in “information for the teachers” in the textbook in “good” way to help teachers to incorporate the audio visual material. In the textbook, there are exercises to practice, test, and review vocabulary words and also exercises are for grammar points.

Table and Figure 5: Teachers' Opinion about Information for the Teachers

Excellent	Good	Adequate	Poor	Totally Lacking
13.65%	35.55%	28.86%	14.15%	15.5%

Third part of the questionnaire was about context and this part consists of total nine items. From results, it can be concluded that the textbook is appropriate for the curriculum and it is according to students’ needs. English textbook of grade ten meets with the course goals and there is no offensive material in the book. Examples and illustration in the textbook are good and understandable. The text selection of is very good because students enjoy it and teachers have enough proficiency to use supportive material.

Table and Figure 6: Teachers' Opinion about Context

Excellent	Good	Adequate	Poor	Totally Lacking
14.79%	43.89%	30.79%	7.14%	3.32%

7. Conclusion

From results, it can be concluded that the textbook is appropriate for the curriculum and it is designed per students' needs and interest. Text, examples and explanations are so good that everyone can easily understand it. The organization of the text is logical and textbook is consistent with course goals. According to teachers' view cover of the textbook and visual imagery are good but in fact quality of images in the textbook is not high aesthetic quality because images are black and white and non-recognizable. Sufficient information for the teachers is helpful for them to understand objectives, methodologies, techniques, examples to teach text, vocabulary and grammar. The content of the textbook is organized easy to difficult and this also serves as a window to learn target language culture. There are also topics of real life issues in the textbook.

Vocabulary words are included in such a way that the lesson reinforces their meaning and the students are able to understand vocabulary words easily. There are also some examples of learning of grammar rules in context but most grammar rules are taught in inductive way. Text and exercises promote the critical thinking of the students. Though majority of teachers are satisfied with this textbook but minority of teachers who do not agree with this, cannot be neglected. There is still need to improve textbook. Finally, it can be said that the overall quality of textbook is good.

This study would be useful for teachers, students, textbook designers and educational experts. They may review the content of teaching according to student's needs. Teachers may also change the teaching methodologies as well as assessment methods in English language teaching classrooms. Teachers may adopt appropriate methods according to student's level.

These results of this study are based on data collected from teachers, for better evaluation of textbook it is needed to evaluate English textbook both from views of students and teachers. There is a need to evaluate grade-x English textbook at a large scale by keeping in view content, vocabulary and grammar, exercise and activities, physical make up and information for the teachers separately in detail. The number of

participants in this study is small so it is needed to evaluate it with a large sample size from the whole Punjab. This is also needed to evaluate it in qualitative way with quantitative study.

References

1. Abbas, D. M. (1993). *Textbook Development in Pakistan and United Kingdom*. Lahore: Sang-i-Meel.
2. Aftab, A. (2012). *English Language Textbook Evaluation in Pakistan*. Birmingham: School of English, Drama and American & Canadian Studies College of Arts and Law University of Birmingham.
3. Ahmad Ali, M. T. (2015). An Evaluation of Elementary Level English Textbooks of Punjab Govt. Schools in Punjab. *International Journal of English Language Teaching*, 22-34.
4. Akhtar, M. (2016, September 05). *Importance of English in Pakistan Essay*. Retrieved from ILM.Com: <http://ilm.com.pk/pakistan/pakistan-information/importance-of-english-in-pakistan-essay/>
5. Allwright, R. (1990). *What Do We Want Teaching Material For?* Oxford: Oxford University Press.
6. Ashe, J. J. (1982). *Learning and other language through actions: the complete teachers guide book*. Los Gatos CA: Sky Oaks.
7. BB, A. B. (1983). *The Problems of Inconsiderate Texts*. Rockville: American Speech Language Association.
8. Chall, J. (1991). *Should Textbooks Challenge Students?* New York: Teachers College Press.
9. Cody, C. (1986). *A Policy Maker's Guide to Textbook Selection*. Alexandria: National Association of State Boards of Educations.
10. Cole, J. (1981). *The Textbook in American Society*. Washington: Library of Congress.
11. Coleman, H. (2010). *Teaching and Learning in Pakistan: The Role of Language in Education*. Islamabad: The British Council.
12. Cunningsworth, A. (1984). *Evaluation and Selection EFL Teaching Material*. London: Heinemann Education Books.
13. Davis, j. (1990). *Textbook Futures*. London: Times Educational Supplements.
14. Demiral, P. O. (2016). *Textbook Evaluation Checklist: Questionnaire*. Nicosia: Cyprus International University.

15. Ebel, R. L. (1991). *Essentials of Educational Measurement*. New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India.
16. *English Language Learning Forum*. (2016, September 01). Retrieved from English language learning forum: <http://englishlanguagelearningforum.blogspot.com/2009/03/elt-in-pakistan.html>
17. Fitzgerald, F. (1979). *American Revised: History Schools Books in the Twentieth Century*. New York: Vintage Books.
18. Garton, A. (1996). *Science Move-2*. Melbourne Australia: Heinemann.
19. Gay, L. R. (1985). *Educational Evaluation & Measurement*. Columbus Charles E. Merrill Publishing Company.
20. Gohar, N. H. (2008). *Textbook Development*. Lahore: Murad Publications.
21. Gronlund Norman E., L. R. (1990). *Measurement and Evaluation in Teaching*. New York: Mac Millin Publishing Company.
22. Hale, K. L. (1972). *Some Questions about Anthropological Linguistics: The Role Native Knowledge*. New York: Random House.
23. Hartley, J. (1980). *Designing Instructional Texts*. Washington: National Educational Association.
24. Herliby, J. G. (1992). *The Textbook Controversy*. New Jersey: Ablex Publishing Company
25. Hirsch, E. (1987). *Cultural Literacy*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
26. Irvin, E. (1989). *Reading and the Middle School Student*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
27. J, B. (1983). *The Process of Education*. New York: Vintage Books.
28. L.R Gay, G. E. (2008). *Educational Research*. New York: Pearson Education.
29. Lewis, B. (1989). *K-3 Apache Language Assessment*. Arizona: Whiterive Unified School District.
30. Martin, W. (1966). *Curriculum Improvement and Innovations: A Partnership of Students*. Cambridge: School Teachers and Research Scholars.
31. Pakistan, M. o. (2006, September 15). *National Curriculum for English Language Grade I-XII*. Retrieved from bisep.com: <http://bisep.com.pk/downloads/Grade-V/SLO/English-SLO-G-V.pdf>
32. Pearson, J. (1969). *Education in the State: Historical Development and Outlook*. Washington: National Educational Association.
33. *Procedures for Textbook and Instructional Material Selections*. (1976). Arlington: Educational Research Service.
34. R.C, A. (19984). *Learning to Read in American Schools: Basal Readers and Content Text*. Hill Sate: Erlbaum, N.J.
35. R.L Thorndike, E. H. (1997). *Measurement and Evaluation in Psychology and Education*. New York: John Wiley & Son. Inc.

36. Ravitch, D. (1987). *What Do Our 17-Year Olds Know?* New York: A Happer and Row.
37. Shafqat Naseem, S. K. (2015). Evaluation of English Textbook in Pakistan: A Case Study of Punjab Textbook for Ninth Class. *European Journal of English Language and Literature Studies*, 24-42.
38. Shahid, S. (2008). *Textbook Development*. Lahore: Majeed Book Depot.
39. Shahid, S. (2008). *Textbook Development*. Lahore: Majeed Book Depot.
40. Shahid, S. (2008). *Textbook Selection and Evaluation*. Lahore: Majeed Book Depot.
- 41.Sizer, T. (1984). *Horace's Compromise: The Dilemma of the American High Schools*. Boston: Houghton-Mafflin.
42. Skieroso, A. (n.d.). *Textbook Selection and Evaluation*. Boston: Heinle and Heinle.
43. Bibliography\1 1033 Shafqat Naseem, S. K. (July 2015). Evaluation of English Textbook in Pakistan: A Case Study of Punjab Textbook for Ninth Class. *European Journal of English and Literature Studies*, 24-42.
44. Shamim, F. 2008 Trends, Issues and Challenges in English Language Education in Pakistan. *Asian Pacific Journal of Education* 28 (3), 235-249
45. Tyson, H. (1988). *A Conspiracy of Good Intentions: America's Textbook Fiasco*. Washington: Council for Basic Education.
46. Vishat, S. (1993). *Theory of Educational Evaluation*. New Delhi: Anmol Publishing PVT. Ltd.
47. Williams, D. (1983). *Criteria for ESL Textbook Evaluation*. Nigeria: Bello University.
48. Wilson, G. A. (1995). *Conversational Navago Workbook. An Introductory Course for Non Native Speakers*. Blanding UT: Conversation Navago Publications.
49. Wirsma, W. J. (1990). *Educational Measurement and Testing*. London: Allayn and Bacon.

Appendix A

Textbook Evaluation Questionnaire

Textbook Title: English -X
 Publisher: PTBB Lahore
 Student Language Level: 10th grade
 Date of Publication: 2016

School: _____

I. Textbook

Please Encircle Desired Option

Excellent	Good	Adequate	Poor	Totally Lacking
4	3	2	1	0

A. Content

1. Is the subject matter presented either topically or functionally in a logical and organized manner? 4 3 2 1 0
2. Does the content serve as a window into learning about the target language culture (American, British, etc.)? 4 3 2 1 0
3. Are the reading selections authentic pieces of language? 4 3 2 1 0
4. Compared to texts for native speakers, does the content contain real-life issues that challenge the reader to think critically about his/her worldview? 4 3 2 1 0
5. Are the text selections representative of the variety of literary genres, and do they contain multiple sentence structures? 4 3 2 1 0

B. Vocabulary and Grammar

1. Are the grammar rules presented in a logical manner and in increasing order of difficulty? 4 3 2 1 0
2. Are the new vocabulary words presented in a variety of ways (e.g. glosses, multi-glosses, appositives)? 4 3 2 1 0
3. Are the new vocabulary words presented at an appropriate rate so that the text is understandable and so that students are able to retain new vocabulary? 4 3 2 1 0
4. Are the new vocabulary words repeated in subsequent lessons to reinforce their meaning and use? 4 3 2 1 0
5. Are students taught top-down techniques for learning new vocabulary words? 4 3 2 1 0

Excellent	Good	Adequate	Poor	Totally Lacking
4	3	2	1	0

C. Exercises and Activities

1. Are there interactive and task-based activities that require students to use new vocabulary to communicate? 4 3 2 1 0
2. Do instructions in the textbook tell students to read for comprehension? 4 3 2 1 0
3. Are top-down and bottom-up reading strategies used? 4 3 2 1 0
4. Are students given sufficient examples to learn top-down techniques for reading comprehension? 4 3 2 1 0
5. Do the activities facilitate students' use of grammar rules by creating situations in which these rules are needed? 4 3 2 1 0
6. Does the text make comprehension easier by addressing one new concept at a time instead of multiple new concepts? 4 3 2 1 0
7. Do the exercises promote critical thinking of the text? 4 3 2 1 0

D. Attractiveness of the Text and Physical Make-up

1. Is the cover of the book appealing? 4 3 2 1 0
2. Is the visual imagery of high aesthetic quality? 4 3 2 1 0
3. Are the illustrations simple enough and close enough to the text that they add to its meaning rather than detracting from it? 4 3 2 1 0
4. Is the text interesting enough that students will enjoy reading it? 4 3 2 1 0

II. This Section is about "Information for Teachers" in the Textbook to help the Teachers**A. General Features**

1. Does the information for the teacher help teachers to understand the objectives and methodology of the text? 4 3 2 1 0
2. Are the correct answers given for the exercises in the textbook? 4 3 2 1 0

B. Background Information

1. Are teachers shown how to teach students to use cues from morphology and context to assist them in lexical inference? 4 3 2 1 0
2. Is there a list of true and false vocabulary words of common origin? 4 3 2 1 0

C. Methodological Guidance

1. Are teachers given techniques for activating students' background knowledge before reading the text? 4 3 2 1 0

-
2. Are teachers given adequate examples for teaching students to preview, skim, scan, summarize, and to find the main idea? 4 3 2 1 0
 3. Does the information for teachers suggest a clear, concise method for teaching each lesson? 4 3 2 1 0

D. Supplementary Exercises and Materials

1. Does the information for the teachers give instructions on how to incorporate audio-visual material produced for the textbook? 4 3 2 1 0
2. Does the information for the teachers provide teachers with exercises to practice, test, and review vocabulary words? 4 3 2 1 0
3. Does the information for the teachers provide additional exercises for reinforcing grammar points in the text? 4 3 2 1 0

III. Context

1. Is the textbook appropriate for the curriculum? 4 3 2 1 0
2. Does the text meet with the course goals? 4 3 2 1 0
3. Is the textbook appropriate for the students who will be using it? 4 3 2 1 0
4. Is the text free of material that might be unpleasant? 4 3 2 1 0
5. Are the examples and explanations understandable? 4 3 2 1 0
6. Will students enjoy reading the text selections? 4 3 2 1 0
7. Will the content meet students' felt needs for learning English or can it be adapted for this purpose? 4 3 2 1 0
8. Are the textbook and teacher's information for the teachers appropriate for the teacher who will be teaching from them? 4 3 2 1 0
9. Is the teacher proficient enough in English to use the information for the teachers? 4 3 2 1 0

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of English Language Teaching shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)}](#).